

THE EFFICIENCY OF THE METHOD OF DEVELOPING THE MOTOR ABILITIES OF GIRLS AGED 6-7 IN THE LESSONS OF THE ACCENTED DIRECTION

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the results of a pedagogical experiment to improve the motor abilities of 6-7 year old girls in physical education lessons with the introduction of an accentuated method of directed increase in their physical status.

Improving the quality of education is one of the urgent problems of pedagogical science in the Republic of Uzbekistan, the solution of which is closely related to the modernization of the content of education and the optimization of pedagogical technologies in the educational process. (5.7)

The process of physical education in general education schools on the basis of which children 's interest in practicing selected types of children's sports is formed and provides for the creation of a basis for basic physical training, the formation of a fund of motor skills in order to experimentally substantiate effective means, forms and methods of educating physical qualities.

To address the issues of intensification of the process of physical education, many authors (1.2.3.) suggest using selective physical activity during sensitive periods of development of their motor abilities, which is the most favorable period for a targeted impact on their physical abilities.

The annual monitoring of the motor fitness of children enrolled in school revealed a relatively low satisfactory level of physical status, which creates problems for the coaching staff of children's sports schools that conduct professional selection of children for children's sports.

In order to solve the tasks set, it seemed interesting to identify the level of physical development of girls in the first year of study in the school education system.

The organization of the experiment was based on the scheme of comparative pedagogical research with the participation of control and experimental groups, where first-graders of two secondary schools took part, the results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Indicators of the physical development of girls in the first year of schooling

Age years	N	body length (cm)	body weight (kg)	OGK (cm)
6	26	111.5±4.6	19.8±1.9	56.8±3.9
7	32	117.8±4.9	21.7±1.7	61.1±3.3

In the experimental groups, in agreement with the pedagogical leadership of the schools, daily physical culture and sports events and accentuated physical education lessons were held by graduate students of the Faculty of Physical Education who are in teaching practice at this school. In the educational process, the developed author's program was introduced, aimed at improving the motor qualities of girls, with constant pedagogical and medical control of exercise tolerance with testing of motor qualities at the end of each quarter during the academic year.

Monitoring analysis revealed that during the period of the experiment the level of somatometric characteristics of the studied girls of the experimental group increased significantly to a statistically significant level. So, body length, reflecting the nature of the formation of the child's body and tending to a significant annual increase, in girls increased by 6.3 cm ($P < 0.01$), while it was found that body weight by 7 years increases in relation to 6 years by an average of 1.9 kg ($P < 0.01$). The circumference of the chest by the end of the experiment increased from 56,8 cm to 61.1 cm and amounted to a difference of 4.3 cm, ($P < 0.01$), (4.6)

An important pedagogical task of physical education is to increase the level of motor fitness of children. Without knowing the initial levels of development of the motor abilities of a growing organism, it is impossible to evaluate the results of targeted pedagogical activities and plan the process of improving their motor abilities in the future.

In this regard, a monitoring analysis of the motor fitness of children of the first year of schooling was carried out in quarters, where the battery of tests was borrowed from the state standards for physical education, the test results are presented in table 2.

An analysis of the initial indicators revealed that 30 m the girls overcame the distance, on average, in 7.2 ± 0.5 sec. The physical quality of dexterity was assessed according to the 3 x 10m shuttle run test, where the result for girls was 10.9 ± 0.6 seconds. Accentuated activities carried out during the pedagogical experiment made it possible to increase the results of girls by 6.5%

Table 2

Annual dynamics of motor readiness of girls aged 6-7

No.	Tests	H E T I N E R T A N D										
		I		II		%	III		%	IV		%
		$\bar{X}$	σ	$\bar{X}$	σ		$\bar{X}$	σ		$\bar{X}$	σ	
1	Running 30 m. With.	7.2	0.5	7.1	0.6	1.4	6.8	0.7	5.6	6.7	0.6	7.1
2	Long jump s \ m, sec.	99.2	11.0	102.1	10.9	2.9	112.4	11.7	11.8	114.6	11.9	13.5

3	Throwing a tennis ball	10.4	3.4	11.6	3.2	10.4	12.8	3.9	18.8	13.6	3.5	23.6
4	Flexion extension of the arms, times	4.0	1.1	4.3	0.9	4.7	5.1	1.2	11.6	5.2	1.1	22.1
5	Shuttle run 3x10 m.s.	10.9	0.6	10.8	0.7	1.0	10.4	0.6	4.6	10.2	0.7	6.5
6	Raising the body, times	7.3	3.1	7.6	2.8	4.0	9.1	3.2	19.8	9.2	3.2	20.7

Re-testing of speed qualities at the end of the second quarter in the group of girls showed a tendency to a slight improvement by 0.1 sec. (1.4%) ($p > 0.05$),

Throughout the third quarter, where lessons in athletics and games prevailed, the indicators of speed capabilities of girls increased significantly to 6.8 ± 0.7 seconds. (5.6%). Repeated studies at the end of the school year revealed that the speed capabilities of the studied girls improved significantly by - 7.1%.

Analysis of the results of the speed-strength capabilities of girls based on the results in standing long jumps, the initial indicator was 99.2 ± 11.0 cm. At the end of the second quarter, the result of the girls improved by 2.9%. If we take into account that the motor activity of children of this age period is largely associated with jumping and running, it becomes obvious that the speed-strength qualities of children must be given close attention in the educational process. The complex of developed pedagogical measures aimed at improving the studied motor quality allowed to significantly improve them in girls by 11.8%, with a subsequent progressive increase in results in children by the end of the school year, respectively, by 13.5%.

A significant amount of time was devoted to the strength capabilities of girls, where in physical education classes, complexes of the simplest physical exercises aimed at their strength training were offered.

The analysis of test indicators in the test of flexion and extension of the arms in the lying position, the result was 4.0 ± 1.1 times, respectively. The positive dynamics of the increase in the strength abilities of girls is clearly visible in the quarters, where by the end of the second quarter by - 4.7%, in the third by - 11.3% and by the end of the academic year, the improvement was 22.1% and 18.9%. Girls showed a significant increase up to 23.1%. A similar picture is observed in the test indicators of lifting the body from the supine position, where the increase was 20.7%.

Difficult- coordinated motor actions like throwing a tennis ball at a distance in girls and boys amounted to 10.4 ± 3.4 m, at the end of the second quarter there was an unreliable improvement in the result by 0.8 m.

The introduction of accentuated motor tasks with a training orientation in physical culture classes and carried out by future specialists in physical culture made it possible to significantly increase the performance of girls up to 12.8 ± 3.9 m, where the increase was 18.8%.

Completing the training in the first year, the results of repeated studies confirmed our earlier hypothesis that physical exercises focused on the development of the necessary motor qualities with a training orientation give a significant increase in performance, which is confirmed by an improvement in girls' performance by -23.6%.

The mathematical and statistical processing of the results obtained during the pedagogical experiment with girls of the first year of study in the school education system revealed the highest coefficient of variation in girls in the flexibility test (54.2%), flexion and extension of the arms in the lying position (42.8%) and lifting the torso from the supine position (42.1%). (2.5)

According to the data of physical development in girls, the highest rank of influence is body weight (27%) and body length (22%). This determined the need for a correlation analysis of indicators of physical development and motor fitness of the studied contingent, providing a scientifically based approach to the complex of means, in identifying valid control standards.

The correlation analysis of the relationship between the physical development and motor fitness of girls (Table 3), revealed a relationship between speed indicators in running 30 m and standing long jumps, ($r = 0.61$). Weak connection measured between body weight and torso lifting from the supine position ($r = 0.34$), flexion and extension of the arms in the lying position and shuttle running ($r = -0.47$), shuttle running and general flexibility. ($r = 0.34$),

The conducted pedagogical experiment made it possible to reveal the insufficient level of the physical status of children of the first year of study and requires:

- taking into account the individual characteristics of physical development and physical fitness of children of the first year of study, allowing to determine the groups of students by the level of their motor fitness in the process of conducting physical education lessons;
- normalization of the volume and intensity of motor activity corresponding to the biological needs of the children's body;
- regular implementation of medical and pedagogical supervision for the health of children.

Table 3

Correlation coefficients between indicators of physical development and motor fitness of girls of the first year learning in the school system

No.	Name of tests	r	
1.	Running 30 m- shuttle run	0.62	
2.	Running 30 m- long jump	0.61	
3.	Throwing a tennis ball - flexion and extension of the arms in a lying position	0.44	
4.	Flexion and extension of the arms in an emphasis lying down - shuttle run	-0.52	

5.	Flexion and extension of the arms in an emphasis lying down - running 30 м	-0.47	-
6.	Shuttle Run - General Flexibility	-0.38	-
7.	Running 30 м- general flexibility	-0.48	-

The foregoing allows us to conclude that the teaching staff conducting physical education classes with children of primary school age, relying on a constant monitoring analysis of their health status, search for effective innovative ways to implement the tasks and timely make appropriate adjustments to the educational process.

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